

An Efficient Combined Meta-Heuristic Algorithm for Solving the Traveling Salesman Problem

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Abstract

The traveling salesman problem (TSP) is one of the most important NP-hard Problems and probably the most famous and extensively studied problem in the field of combinatorial optimization. In this problem, a salesman is required to visit each of n given nodes once and only once, starting from any node and returning to the original place of departure. This paper presents an efficient evolutionary optimization algorithm developed through combining imperialist competitive algorithm and lin-kernighan algorithm called (MICALK) in order to solve the TSP. The MICALK is tested on 44 TSP instances involving from 24 to 1655 nodes from the literature so that 26 best known solutions of the benchmark problem are also found by our algorithm. Furthermore, the performance of MICALK is compared with several metaheuristic algorithms, including GA, BA, IBA, ICA, GSAP, ABO, PSO and BCO on 32 instances from TSPLIB. The results indicate that the MICALK performs well and is quite competitive with the above algorithms.

Keywords: Imperialist Competitive Algorithm; NP-hard Problems; Lin-Kernighan Algorithm; Traveling Salesman Problem.

1. Introduction

There are a lot of research studies in the field of logistics, ranging from the assignment problems to complex dynamic routing problems. Among the prominent problems in the field of distribution and logistics, the traveling salesman problem (TSP) has arguably been one of the most widely investigated problems of combinatorial optimization in recent years and there have been many research studies to provide a better solution for this problem (Lawler et al., 1985). A large number of problems like the TSP with pickup and delivery, time windows TSP, multi-depot TSP, multiple TSP, vehicle routing problem and so on have arisen from this problem (YousefiKhoshbakht, Didehvar, & Rahmati, 2014). Besides, it has many applications in dealing with other problems, including the Print press scheduling (Rathinam & Sengupta, 2006), School bus routing problem (Svestka & Huckfeldt, 1973), Interview scheduling (Angel et al., 1972), Hot rolling scheduling (Brummit & Stentz, 1998), Design of global navigation satellite system surveying networks (Tang et al., 2000), etc.

The TSP can be represented by a complete graph $G = (N, A)$ where N is the set of nodes, and A is the set of arcs fully connecting the nodes. Let c_{ij} be the length of the arc (i, j) , which is the distance between nodes i and j . The TSP is the problem of finding a minimal length Hamiltonian circuit, where a Hamiltonian circuit of a graph G is a closed tour visiting once and only once all $n = |N|$ nodes of G , and its length is the sum of the lengths of all the arcs of which it is composed.

There have been important advances in developing exact and heuristic algorithms for solving the TSP. There are several exact algorithms of the TSP such as Cutting Planes algorithm (Laporte & Nobert, 1980), branch-and-cut method (Cordeau, Dell'Amico, & Iori, 2010) and lagrangean relaxation and branch-and-bound algorithm (Mak & Boland, 2007). Since the TSP belongs to the class of NP-complete problems, its solution grows exponentially with the increase in

distribution points. Thus, exact algorithms are not capable of solving problems with large dimensions. On the other hand, heuristics are thought to be more efficient for a complex TSP and have become very popular with researchers. A lot of algorithms have been performed on the TSP including heuristic approaches such as the k -opt approach (Potvin, Lapalme, & Rousseau, 1989), minimum spanning tree (Malik, Rathinam, & Darbha, 2007), self-organizing NN approach (Vakhutinsky & Golden, 1994) and the partitioning approach (Karp, 1977).

Although heuristic methods solve NP-complete problems, they become trapped in local optima and cannot obtain optimum solution. As a result a new kind of algorithm called metaheuristics has been proposed in recent years (Ahmadvand, YousefiKhoshbakht, & Mahmoodi Darani, 2012). These algorithms try to seek high quality solutions while attempting to reduce the computational time. Furthermore, in comparison with heuristic algorithms, because metaheuristics use the randomization concept in search for a solution, this group is more effective in escaping from local optimum and can produce solutions of higher quality. Some of the well-known metaheuristics are the particle swarm optimization (Anantathanavit & Munlin, 2015), neural network (Tarkov, 2015), ant colony optimization (Sedighpour et al., 2013), simulated annealing (Jeong, Kim, & Lee, 2009), neural networks (Jolai & Ghanbari, 2010) and Genetic Reactive Bone Route Algorithm whit Ant Colony System (Yousefikhoshbakht, Malekzadeh, & Sedighpour, 2016).

The ICA is a global search strategy which uses the socio-political competition among empires as a source of inspiration. Like many evolutionary algorithms, the primary ICA may fall into local minimum trap during the search process and it might get far from the global optimum. For this reason, we try to propose an effective two-phase ICA called MICALK by adopting a behavior between rigid regularity and randomness based on pure chance. At the first stage, the TSP is solved by a modified ICA, and at the second stage, Since the Lin-Kernighan algorithm is one of the most effective local search algorithms for solving the TSP, this algorithm is used for improving solutions. In more details, to enhance the global exploration capability, the 2-opt local search with a high probability of α and 0-1 and 1-1 exchanges with low probability β and μ respectively are used. This probability of movement has changed during the search process. The main contributions of the paper are as follows:

ICA to enhance the ability of escaping from a local optimum

- (i) Presenting an effective ICA algorithm for discrete problems
- (ii) Combining the ICA algorithm with a Lin-Kernighan algorithm called MICALK
- (iii) Presenting a new algorithm which is equipped with diversification and intensification mechanisms for solving the TSP.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: in Section 2 we present the basic principle of ICA, Lin-Kernighan (LK) algorithm and then explain the details of the process of the proposed algorithm. In Section 3, the proposed algorithm will be compared with some of the other algorithms on standard problems which are included in the TSP library. The conclusions and the future works are presented in section 4.

2. Solution Method

In this section at first, the classic ICA and LK are explained and then the hybrid of ICA and LK as the proposed algorithm is explained in more detail. Finally, because the MICALK is metaheuristic, parameter setting is presented.

2.1. The basic principle of ICA

During the last three decades, evolutionary optimization methods inspired by natural processes have shown good performance in solving combinatorial optimization problems. These algorithms have become increasingly popular through the development and utilization of intelligent paradigms in the design of advanced information systems. When the task is optimized within complex domains of data or information, nature-inspired approaches such as swarm or flocking

intelligence (bird flocks or fish schools inspired particle swarm optimization), artificial immune systems which mimic the biological ones, ant colonies (ants' foraging behaviors gave rise to ant colony optimization), or optimized performance of bees and so on are widely used to solve engineering optimization problems.

ICA, which proved to be capable of obtaining acceptable performance of some of benchmark cost functions is one of the newest algorithms created in the recent decades. This new optimization algorithm was first used by Atashpaz Gargari et al to solve the combinational optimization problems in 2007 (Atashpaz Gargari & Lucas, 2007). In recent years, the ICA has been successfully applied to several NP-hard combinatorial optimization problems, namely, TSP (YousefiKhoshbakht & Sedighpour, 2013), recommender systems (Sepehri Rad & Lucas, 2008), designing skeletal structures (Kaveh & Talatahari, 2010), and many other optimization problems such as the characterization of elasto-plastic properties of materials, designing optimal layout for factories, adaptive antenna arrays, intelligent recommender systems, and optimal controller for industrial and chemical processes (Shokrollahpour, Zandieh, & Dorri, 2010). This evolutionary optimization strategy has shown great performance in both convergence rate and better global optimum achievement. Furthermore, the proposed evolutionary optimization algorithms are generally inspired by modeling the natural processes and other aspects of species evolution, especially human evolution, which have not been considered up to now. The method proposed in this work uses socio-political evolution of human as a source of inspiration for developing a powerful optimization strategy. What is more important, the ICA considers the imperialism as a level of human social evolution and by mathematically modeling this complicated political and historical process harnesses it as a tool for evolutionary optimization.

The ICA is a novel global search strategy which uses imperialism and imperialistic competition process as a source of inspiration. This algorithm is based on the fact that in a real world, countries try to extend their power over other countries in order to use their resources and bolster their own government. The first step in ICA is to generate an initial population like other evolutionary algorithms. The population set includes a number of feasible solutions called a 'country', which corresponds to the term 'chromosome' in the GA method. These countries are of two types: colonies and imperialists that altogether form some empires. As it is shown in Figure 1 (Atashpaz Gargari & Lucas, 2007), bigger and stronger empires have more colonies than smaller and weaker ones.

Figure 1. The Initial Empires

After initial empires are formed, their colonies start moving toward their relevant imperialist country. This movement is a simple model of assimilation policy which was pursued by some of the imperialist states. If one of the colonies possesses more power than its relevant imperialist after this movement, they will exchange their positions. To begin the competition between empires, the total objective function of each empire should be calculated. It depends on the objective function of both an imperialist and its colonies. Imperialistic competition among these empires forms the basis of the proposed evolutionary algorithm. During this competition, weak empires collapse and powerful ones take the possession of their colonies - Figure 2 (Atashpaz Gargari & Lucas, 2007). The empire, which has lost all its colonies, will collapse. At last, the most powerful empire will take the possession of other empires and will win the competition. In other words, imperialistic competition hopefully converges to a state in which there exists only one empire and its colonies are in the same position and have the same cost as the imperialist. Figure 3 shows the flowchart of the basic ICA.¹

Figure 2. Eliminate the weakest colony of the weakest empire

Figure 3. Flowchart of the ICA

¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Imperialist-competitive-algorithm-flowchart.jpg>

2.2. Lin-Kernighan Algorithm

The enormous literature on meta-heuristics indicates that a promising approach for obtaining high-quality solutions is to couple a local search algorithm with a mechanism to generate initial solutions. A simple example of this type of algorithm is the 2-opt algorithm. This algorithm starts with a feasible tour and continues by omitting two arcs of the tour, which are not adjacent and then connects them again by another method in such a way that the new tour length is shorter. It can be noted that there are several routes for connecting nodes and producing the tour again, but a state that satisfies the problem's constraints is acceptable. Omitting and reconnecting two arcs are repeated until no improving 2-opt is found. Besides, the 2-opt algorithm is a unique case of the ω -opt algorithm, where in each step ω links of the current tour are replaced by ω links in such a way that a shorter tour is achieved. The number of operations to test all ω -exchanges increases quickly as the number of nodes increases. The time complexity of testing ω -exchange is equal to $O(n^\omega)$ in which there is no nontrivial upper bound of the number of ω -exchanges.

However, since there are weaknesses, the value of ω and what ω to use to achieve the best compromise between running time and quality of the solution must be specified in advance. The Lin-Kernighan algorithm is a generalization of this simple principle form and is one the most effective algorithms for solving the TSP. This algorithm removed this disadvantage by introducing a powerful variable ω -opt algorithm in which the value of ω is changed during its execution. At each iteration the algorithm considers a growing set of potential exchanges which start with $r = 2$. These exchanges are chosen in such a way that a feasible tour may be formed at any stage of the process. Then, the problem is examined for ascending values of ω and the algorithm decides what the value of ω should be. If an interchange of ω links succeeds in finding a new shorter tour, then the actual tour is replaced with the new tour. This continues until some stopping conditions are satisfied.

2.3. Our approach

In order to apply the proposed algorithm on the TSP, at the first stage, feasible solutions or primitive countries should be introduced in a way which is compatible with the construction of the mentioned problem. Therefore, a bisection array shown in Figure 4 is used. In this array, the visited nodes are ordered from left to right in the first section and the value of the objective function is shown in the second section.

1	9	2	10	3	11	5	12	4	13	6	14	7	8	26
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Figure 4. A Country in ICA

Therefore, a defined number of primitive solutions (r) must be randomly generated and the values of the objective function f_i for each $i=1, \dots, r$ must be obtained. Then, these solutions and their values are imported to matrix D in which every row shows a primitive solution and its value of the objective function. It should be noted that using a random construction at this level leads to obtaining solutions which have an irregular construction in feasible space. Then, m countries which have better objective function are selected and are called empire countries. Furthermore, the number of colonies devoted to each empire j is calculated by the formula (1).

$$k_j = \text{int}[(1 - \frac{f_j}{\sum_{i=1}^m f_i}) \times (r - m)] \quad (1)$$

This formula leads that more colonies are allocated to empires with fewer objective functions and as a result a bigger empire is formed. The Int function used in the formula is the floor

function which causes the allocation of an integer number of colonies to each empire. It should be noted that allocating colonies to empires is conducted randomly and if some countries might not belong to any empire due to the property of the Int function, these countries are allocated to the most powerful empire. After the empires are formed, each empire increases its quality, using the imperialist countries which play local optima role. What is worthy of note is the fact that since a lot of possible points are combined with local optima, we must use an absorption function which includes a randomization concept so that the results of combinations will not yield a very similar response. To achieve this goal, we have utilized a novel and innovative method. As an example, first, two possible responses [5 2 9 4 8 3 1 6 7] and [9 2 7 6 5 3 1 8 4] are considered as imperialist and colony respectively. Then, a random number between 2 and $n-1$ is selected (n is the number nodes of instance and is 9 here). After that, some nodes equal to the selected number are chosen from the colonies and are arranged according to the order of the imperialist countries. If the selected random number between 1 and 8 is 4, then 4 nodes are randomly chosen from the colonies like 2, 6, 5, and 3. Then, their order in imperialist country which is 5, 2, 3, and 6 in the example is found. Therefore, the new result for the colony will be [9 5 7 2 3 6 1 8 4]. The absorption function is performed for all colonies in comparison to imperialist countries and the results and the values are replaced with the best results and the values obtained in the current iteration provided that the new results are better.

At the next stage, p percent of countries experience a revolution. This causes variations in colonies in each empire and if possible their quality increases at each stage. The proposed methods for this stage are the 0-1 Exchange move. In this move, a candidate node is removed from its original route and is inserted in the best position. The replacement is done if the new results are better than the previous ones.

Most successful meta-heuristic methods have paid attention to global search and search in the whole solution space as far as possible. As the algorithm proceeds, it moves to better solutions and the global search switches to a local search. We have factored in this issue too, and have represented the probability of 0-1, 1-1- and 2-opt move with α , β and μ respectively so that $\alpha + \beta + \mu = 1$. In the 1-1-Exchange, two nodes are randomly selected and exchanged with each other. Finally, in the 2-Opt move, two non-adjacent edges are replaced by two other edges. It should be noted that there are several routes for connecting nodes and producing the tour again, but a state which satisfies the problem's constraints is acceptable. Note that although 2-opt local search as a powerful global search algorithm is more used at the beginning of algorithm for global search, 0-1 and 1-1 exchanges are more applied at the end of the algorithm because these algorithms might lead to premature convergence to suboptimal regions. In other words, before the algorithm finishes a complete global search, it tends to adopt a local search and consequently relatively weak results are attained. Therefore, whenever the algorithm continues the probability of α decreases and the probability of β and μ increases. Adding this behavior to the imperialist algorithm revolution policy leads to creating the proper conditions for the algorithm to escape from local peaks. Thus, as mentioned before, the probability of using the 2-opt, 0-1 and 1-1 exchanges at the first step of the proposed algorithm is considered 0.50, 0.25 and 0.25 and then during the other steps of the proposed algorithm, they are gradually converted to 0.20, 0.40 and 0.40.

After the results and the values are calculated for all colonies, these countries might have a better objective value compared to their respective imperialists. Therefore, a colony with the best value in each empire is chosen and if it possesses a better objective value, it replaces an imperialist country. If there are a few colonies with the same objective value, one of them is chosen randomly and is compared with an imperialist country in the empire. From this stage up to the end of the algorithm, there will not be any change in objective functions of feasible values. Therefore, the best results and values of the objective function must be saved. For this purpose, two variables are chosen in order to save the best results and values until the current iteration. In each iteration, after the imperialist countries are replaced, the best results and values for the imperialist countries are

chosen as the best current results. If the new attained value is better than the value of the previous iteration, local search is conducted and the previous results and values are replaced with the new results and values. Up to this stage in the algorithm, the purpose is conducting a general search to locate important areas for algorithm convergence. Now, important areas must be identified and the population must be converged toward them. After this stage, part of the initial population moves toward these areas. The power of empires is assessed at this stage. In imperialist competitions, more powerful empires must expand their territory through occupying other countries. In order to achieve this goal, the power of the empire is calculated using formula 2.

$$h_j = f_j + \lambda(s_j) \quad j = 1, \dots, m \quad (2)$$

In this formula h_j , s_j , and λ represent empire's total power, the average objective function of the colonies in each empire, and the [0 1] impact coefficient, which determines the relative power of a colony compared to an empire, respectively. A weaker empire loses its power by losing its weakest colony to the strongest empire. At this stage, the final condition is checked and if it is met, the algorithm ends. Otherwise, the algorithm is iterated by returning to the absorption function step. To end the proposed algorithm, one of the two conditions must be met: the iteration of algorithm n times or the survival of just one empire. These conditions are checked at the end of each algorithm iteration. If any one of the conditions is met, the algorithm ends and the obtained results and values up to now are considered as the best values and results of the algorithm.

Moreover, in order to prevent the ICA from getting trapped in stagnation, we used a local searching algorithm when the algorithm attained a better solution compared to previous iterations. In fact, the probability of finding better solutions near a good solution is relatively high. There exist many algorithms for the local search and they have of course their pros and cons. Since Lin-Kernighan algorithm is simple and it is one of the most successful methods for generating optimal or near optimal solutions for the TSP, we have used it in this study. The main steps of MICALK are summarized in the pseudo-code given in Figure 5.

- Step 1: Generate r random solutions of the TSP and initialize the empires.
- Step 2: Move the colonies toward their relevant imperialist by the proposed absorption function.
- Step 3: Change p percent of colonies as revolution by the 0-1 Exchange move.
- Step 4: If there is a colony in an empire which has better cost than the imperialist, exchange the positions of that colony and the imperialist.
- Step 5: Compute the total cost of all empires by formula (2).
- Step 6: Pick the weakest colony from the weakest empires and give it to the best empire (Imperialistic competition).
- Step 7: Eliminate the powerless empires.
- Step 8: If the quality of the best solution is increased in this iteration, apply lin-kernighan algorithm to s and save the best so far solution.
- Step 9: If the iteration of algorithm reaches to n times or the just one empire is reminded, stop, if not go to 2.

Figure 5. The process of MICALK for solving the TSP

2.4 Parameter settings

The proposed MICALK algorithm contains several parameters like other metaheuristics for solving the optimization problems. The quality solutions produced by the MICALK have been dependent on the different values of the user-controlled parameters of the algorithm. In this algorithm, three important parameters exist and their values directly or indirectly affect the performance of the algorithm. For each of the benchmark instances, ten different runs with the selected parameters were performed after the selection of the final parameters. In general, it is not easy to obtain the best combination of algorithm parameters, but a parameter setting procedure is necessary to reach the best balance between the quality of the obtained solutions. These parameters are selected in this paper after thorough testing. All of the parameter values have been determined on the Eil101 by the numerical experiments so that several alternative values for each parameter were tested while all the other values were held constant. It should be noted that only parameters which gave the best computational results concerning the quality of the solution were selected. The details regarding the settings of the parameters and their values are explained in Table 1.

Parameter	Description	Candidate Value	Best Value
p	Number of primitive countries	100, 200, 300, 400, 500	400
m	Number of Imperialist countries	Int $[r/2, r/3, r/4, r/5, r/6]$	Int $[r/4]$
λ	The impact coefficient, which determines the relative power of a colony compared to an empire	0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5	0.2

3. Computational experiments

In this section, first, the algorithms tested on 33 classic benchmark problems for the TSP are presented and then some numerical results of the comparison between the proposed algorithm and some metaheuristic algorithms are given. These algorithms are applied and tested on several Euclidean sample instances of TSPLIB with sizes ranging from 24 to 318 nodes. Because the proposed approach is a metaheuristic algorithm, the results are reported for ten independent runs in which the algorithm was executed until the best solution was iterated 10 times.

The algorithms are coded by *Matlab* language and implemented on a Pentium 4 PC at 3GHZ (1GB RAM). The parameters of the proposed algorithm are selected after thorough testing. A number of different alternative values were tested and the ones selected are those which yielded the best computational results concerning both the quality of the solution and the computational time needed to achieve this solution. Thus, the selected parameters are:

- Number of countries equal to p
- Number of empires equal to $N/5$
- λ is equal to 0.3.

Table 2 shows the results of the proposed algorithm for the TSP benchmark problem instances. In this table, columns 2-6 show the problem size n , the best value result of MICALK (BVR), the worst value result of MICALK (WVR), the average value of MICALK (AV) over the ten runs for each problem, and the best known solutions (BKS), respectively. The seventh column contains the CPU time for each problem (Opt), and the eighth for the relative deviation (RD) where the relative deviation is calculated as $(MICALK - Opt)/Opt \times 100\%$, where MICALK denotes the cost of the optimum found by the proposed algorithm, and Opt is the cost of the optimal solution.

Table 2. Results of MICALK for the TSP							
Instance	N	BVR	WVR	AV	BKS	CPU Time (min)	RD
Eil51	51	426	456	432	426	1.45	0
Berlin52	52	7542	7589	7565	7542	1.43	0
Eil76	76	538	567	543	538	2.22	0
Pr76	76	108363	108925	108553	108159	2.34	0.19
Rat99	99	1211	1308	1262	1211	3.45	0
KroA100	100	21282	21451	21378	21282	3.57	0
KroB100	100	22141	22468	22326	22141	3.52	0
KroC100	100	20749	20989	20890	20749	3.75	0
KroD100	100	21389	21654	21540	21294	3.78	0.47
KroE100	100	22068	22245	22164	22068	3.23	0
Rd100	100	7910	7998	7976	7910	3.02	0
Eil101	101	629	712	699	629	3.52	0
Lin105	105	14379	14599	14556	14379	4.12	0
Pr107	107	44303	44467	44398	44303	4.54	0
Pr124	124	59124	59567	59213	59030	4.67	0.16
Bier127	127	118589	118857	118736	118282	4.62	0.26
Ch130	130	6110	6245	6186	6110	4.75	0
Pr136	136	96772	97546	97290	96772	4.72	0
Pr144	144	58537	58987	58812	58537	4.85	0
Ch150	150	6528	6654	6595	6528	4.61	0
KroA150	150	26524	26989	26734	26524	4.85	0
Pr152	152	73710	73923	73859	73682	5.01	0.04
Rat195	195	2325	2485	2417	2323	7.72	0.09
D198	198	15785	16758	16331	15780	7.95	0.03
KroA200	200	29368	29983	29694	29368	8.32	0.05
KroB200	200	29437	29876	29645	29437	8.94	0
Ts225	225	126940	127435	127293	126643	10.63	0.23
Pr226	226	80745	82879	81598	80369	10.99	0.47
Gil262	262	2393	2578	2467	2378	11.25	0.63
Pr264	264	49842	50156	49989	49135	11.73	1.42
A280	280	2601	2895	2797	2579	12.63	0.85
Pr299	299	48349	48980	48739	48191	13.56	0.33
Rd400	400	15521	16870	16324	15281	32.84	1.57

This table shows that the MICALK can be used to solve the TSP effectively. As table 2 indicates, the maximum relative error and average relative error for 33 test problems are 1.57% and 0.21%, respectively.

Figure 6 shows some of the best solutions searched by the proposed method. In this figure, the horizontal axis represents the x-axis with increasing positive values to the right and the vertical axis represents the y-axis with increasing positive values upward.

Figure 6. Some best routes found by the proposed algorithm

Table 3 shows the results obtained for the second problem instances and presents the comparison of the best results of our algorithm with other published research studies, including genetic algorithm (GA) (Ray, Bandyopadhyay, & Pal, 2004), particle swarm optimization (PSO) (Zhong, Zhang, & Chen, 2007), bee colony optimization (BCO) (Wong, Low, & Chong, 2008), african buffalo optimization (ABO) (Odili & Mohmad Kahar, 2016), genetic simulated annealing ant colony system with particle swarm optimization (GSAP) (Chen & Chien, 2011), ICA (YousefiKhoshbakht & Sedighpour, 2013), bat algorithm (BA) (Osaba et al., 2016) and improved bat algorithm (IBA) (Osaba et al., 2016) in terms of the optimal solution found. The results of this comparison show that the proposed algorithm gains equal solutions with the GA in GR24, Bayg29 and GR48 which are not large scale problems and it gains better solutions than the GA in scale problems such as St70 and KroA100. Furthermore, the results indicate that although the ICA provides a better solution and equal solutions compared with MICALK for seventeen instances, this algorithm obtains worse solutions than MICA for fourteen solutions.

Table 3. Comparison between MICALK and other metaheuristic algorithms

Instance	Size	IBA [33]	BA [33]	GA [28]	ICA [23]	GSAP [32]	ABO [31]	PSO [29]	BCO [30]	MICALK	Optimum
GR24	24	-	-	1272	1272	-	-	-	-	1272	1272
Bayg29	29	-	-	1610	1610	-	-	-	-	1610	1610
GR48	48	-	-	5046	5046	-	-	-	-	5046	5046
ATT48	48	-	-	-	10628	-	-	-	10661	10628	10628
Eil51	51	426	430	-	426	427	426	427	428	426	426
Berlin52	52	7542	7676	-	7542	7542	-	7542	-	7542	7542
ST70	70	675	696	685	677	-	-	-	-	675	675
Eil76	76	539	559	-	538	538	538	540	539	538	538
KroA100	100	21282	21884	21504	21282	21282	21311	21296	21763	21282	21282
KroB100	100	22141	22843	-	22141	22141	22160	-	22637	22141	22141
KroC100	100	20749	20802	-	20749	20749	20755	-	20853	20749	20749
KroD100	100	21294	21727	-	21294	21309	21347	-	21643	21389	21294
KroE100	100	22068	22323	-	22068	22068	22088	-	22450	22068	22068
Eil101	101	646	667	-	629	630	-	-	635	629	629
Lim105	105	-	-	-	14379	14379	-	-	15288	14379	14379
KroA150	150	-	-	-	26524	26524	26526	-	27858	26524	26524
KroB150	150	-	-	-	26154	26130	26169	-	26535	26130	26130
KroA200	200	-	-	-	29379	29383	29370	29563	29961	29368	29368
KroB200	200	-	-	-	29437	29541	29487	-	30350	29487	29437
Pr107	107	44794	44618	-	44303	-	-	-	-	44303	44303
Pr124	124	59412	59627	-	59087	-	-	-	-	59076	59030
Pr136	136	99351	101631	-	96845	-	-	-	-	93812	96772
Pr144	144	58537	58588	-	58537	-	-	-	-	58537	58537
Pr152	152	73921	74172	-	73682	-	73730	-	-	73682	73682
Pr264	264	49756	50256	-	50111	-	-	-	-	49765	49135
Pr299	299	48310	49142	-	49879	-	-	-	-	48299	48191
Li318	318	-	-	-	42487	42487	-	-	44685	42383	42029
Rat575	575	-	-	-	6823	6891	6774	-	-	6773	6773
Rat783	783	-	-	-	8905	8988	8811	-	-	8811	8806
RII323	1323	-	-	-	272341	277642	270480	-	-	270456	270199
F11400	1400	-	-	-	20453	20593	20134	-	-	20132	20127
D1655	1655	-	-	-	64521	64151	62128	-	-	62128	62128

From the comparison between IBA and the proposed algorithm, it can be seen that IBA in nine examples has been able to find the optimum and in eight examples can yield to find solutions with gap of less than 1 percent. However, the proposed MICALK has found better solutions than IBA for larger size of instances. The last powerful algorithm compared to the proposed is IBA. This algorithm can obtain nine out of twenty best solutions, but the MICALK can yield better solutions than IBA in the remaining 11 examples. It should be noted that three reminded algorithms have had a weak performance in general and have not been able to produce the best solutions in most of the examples. In more details, the computational experiments confirm that in general the proposed algorithm provides better results compared to PSO, BA and BCO algorithms in terms of the quality of the solutions and is able to find the best solutions for twenty three out of thirty two in this table.

The evolution of the best solution found by the proposed algorithm is plotted in Figure 7 during a typical execution when solving instance Eil51 and KroB100. In this figure, the horizontal and vertical axes show the number of iterations and gained values of the proposed algorithm respectively. Besides, there is a fast convergence toward the BKS at the beginning of the execution while in the rest of the search the evolution of the BKS is not that fast.

Figure 7. Execution plot, for instance Eil51 (left figure) and KroB100 (right figure)

4. Conclusion

In this paper, a hybrid algorithm called MICALK which combines ICA and Lin-Kernighan algorithm was proposed for solving the TSP. We have also done experiments using two different data sets of TSP instances, including 44 problems with 24–1655 nodes from the TSPLIB. The experimental results indicate that the gap of the proposed algorithm stays on average below 1.6% of the execution time and the MICALK uniformly produces higher performance solutions compared with other competing metaheuristics including GA, BA, IBA, GSAP, ABO, PSO, ICA and BCO on the TSP. It seems that the combination of the proposed algorithm with ant colony system or tabu search will yield better results for large problems of TSP. Applying this method in other combinatorial optimization problems, including the multiple traveling salesmen problem, vehicle routing problem, School bus routing problem and the sequencing of jobs is suggested for future research studies.

References

- Lawler, E.L., Lenstra, J.K., Rinnooy Kan, A.H.G., & Shmoys, D.B. (1985). *The Traveling Salesman Problem*. John Wiley & Sons, New York.
- YousefiKhoshbakht, M., Didehvar, F., & Rahmati, F. (2014). A Combination of Modified Tabu Search and Elite Ant System to Solve the Vehicle Routing Problem with Simultaneous Pickup and Delivery, *Journal of Industrial and Production Engineering*, 31 (2), 65-75.

- Rathinam, S. & Sengupta, R. (2006). Lower and upper bounds for a symmetric Multiple Depot, *Multiple Travelling Salesman Problem*, Research Report, UCB-ITSRR- 2006-2, Institute of Transportation Studies.
- Svestka, J. A. & Huckfeldt, V. E. (1973). "Computational experience with an m-salesman traveling salesman algorithm," *Management Science* 19(7): 790–799.
- Angel, R. D., Caudle, W.L., Noonan, R., & Whinston, A. (1972). "Computer assisted school bus scheduling," *Management Science* 18: 279–288.
- Brummit, B. & Stentz, A. (1998). GRAMMPS: a generalized mission planner for multiple mobile robots. *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on robotics and automation*.
- Tang, L., Liu, J., Rong, A., & Yang, Z. (2000). "A multiple traveling salesman problem model for hot rolling scheduling in Shangai Baoshan Iron & Steel Complex," *European Journal of Operational Research* 124: 267–282.
- Laporte, G. & Nobert, Y. A. (1980). "Cutting planes algorithm for the m-salesmen problem," *Journal of the Operational Research Society* 31: 1017–1023.
- Cordeau, J. F., Dell'Amico, M., & Iori, M. (2010). "Branch-and-cut for the pickup and delivery traveling salesman problem with FIFO loading," *Computers & Operations Research* 37(5): 970-980.
- Mak, V. & Boland, N. (2007). "Polyhedral results and exact algorithms for the asymmetric travelling salesman problem with replenishment arcs," *Discrete Applied Mathematics* 155(16): 2093-2110.
- Potvin, J., Lapalme, G., & Rousseau, J. (1989). "A generalized k-opt exchange procedure for the MTSP," *Information Systems and Operations Research* 27(4): 474–481.
- Malik, W., Rathinam, S., & Darbha, S. (2007). "An approximation algorithm for a symmetric Generalized Multiple Depot," *Multiple Travelling Salesman Problem. Operations Research Letters* 35(6): 747-753,
- Vakhutinsky, I. A. & Golden, L. B. (1994). Solving vehicle routing problems using elastic net, *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on neural network*, 4535–4540,
- Karp, R. M. (1977). "Probabilistic analysis of partitioning algorithms for the traveling salesman problem in the plane," *Mathematics of Operations Research* 2: 209-224.
- Ahmadvand, M., YousefiKhoshbakht, M., & Mahmoodi Darani, N. (2012). Solving the Traveling Salesman Problem by an Efficient Hybrid Metaheuristic Algorithm, *Journal of Advances in Computer Research*, 3 (3), 75-84.
- Anantathanavit, M., & Munlin, M. (2015). Using K-means Radius Particle Swarm Optimization for the Travelling Salesman Problem. *IETE Technical Review*, 1-9.
- Tarkov, M. S. (2015). Solving the traveling salesman problem using a recurrent neural network. *Numerical Analysis and Applications*, 8(3), 275-283.
- Sedighpour, M., Ahmadi, V., YousefiKhoshbakht, M., Didehvar, F., & Rahmati, F. (2013). Solving the Open Vehicle Routing Problem by a Hybrid Ant Colony Optimization, *Kuwait Journal of Science*, 41 (3), 139-162
- Jeong, S. J., Kim, K. S., & Lee, Y. H. (2009). "The efficient search method of simulated annealing using fuzzy logic controller," *Expert Systems with Applications* 36(3), 7099-7103.
- Jolai, F. & Ghanbari, A. (2010). "Integrating data transformation techniques with Hopfield neural networks for solving travelling salesman problem," *Expert Systems with Applications* 37(7), 5331-5335.
- Yousefikhoshbakht, M., Malekzadeh, N., & Sedighpour, M. (2016). Solving the Traveling Salesman Problem Based on The Genetic Reactive Bone Route Algorithm whit Ant Colony System, *International Journal of Production Management and Engineering*, 4 (2), 65-73.
- Atashpaz Gargari, E. & Lucas, C. (2007). Imperialist Competitive Algorithm: An Algorithm for Optimization Inspired by Imperialistic Competition, *IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC 2007)*, 4661 – 4667.

- YousefiKhoshbakht, M. & Sedighpour, M. (2013). New Imperialist Competitive Algorithm to Solve the Traveling Salesman Problem, *International Journal of Computer Mathematics*, 90 (7), 1495-1505.
- Sepehri Rad, H. & Lucas, C. (2008). Application of imperialistic competition algorithm in recommender systems. In 13th international CSI computer conference (CSICC'08), Kish Island, Iran.
- Kaveh, A. & Talatahari, S. (2010). "Optimum design of skeletal structures using imperialist competitive algorithm", *Computers and Structures* 88, 1220–1229.
- Shokrollahpour, E., Zandieh, M., & Dorri, B. (2010). "A novel imperialist competitive algorithm for bi-criteria scheduling of the assembly flowshop problem," *International Journal of Production Research* 1–17.
- Ray, S.S., Bandyopadhyay, S., & Pal, S.K. (2004). "New operators of genetic algorithms for traveling salesman problem," *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Pattern Recognition 2*: 497–500,
- Zhong, W., Zhang, J., & Chen, W. (2007). "A novel discrete particle swarm optimization to solve traveling salesman problem," *Evolutionary Computation* 3283–3287.
- Wong, L. P., Low, M. Y. H., & Chong, C. S. (2008). "A bee colony optimization algorithm for traveling salesman problem," *AICMS*, 818–823.
- Odili, J. B. & Mohmad Kahar, M. N. (2016). "Solving the Traveling Salesman's Problem Using the African Buffalo Optimization," *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*.
- Chen, S. M. & Chien, C. Y. (2011). Solving the traveling salesman problem based on the genetic simulated annealing ant colony system with particle swarm optimization techniques, *Expert Systems with Applications*, 38 (12), 14439–14450.
- Osaba, E., Yang, X.S., Diaz, F., Lopez-Garcia, P., & Carballedo, R. (2016). "An improved discrete bat algorithm for symmetric and asymmetric Traveling Salesman Problems", *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 48, pp.59-71.
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